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Enriching The National Youth Service Corps Programme With Skills: Implications For Reducing Youth Unemployment In Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

The policy of Federal Government of Nigeria that Nigerian Youth who graduate from Universities and Polytechnics should pass through National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) Programme yearly. It is obvious, that this youth programme has given us positive result right from animatic. Therefore, this one year programme should be enriched to enhance its positive results. The paper also hinged on the enrichment of the National Youth Service Crops Programme attached with educational entrepreneurship. The paper also discovered the objectives of NYSC Programme with its purposes. The work also discusses the enrichment achieved through entrepreneurship ideas and skills which the youth was advised to learn on. Finally, the work also discusses the implication of enrichment of NYSC and its youth unemployment that can curbed or reduced through entrepreneurship education among the youths' in Nigeria.

Keywords: Enrichment, entrepreneurial, NYSC Corps Members

INTRODUCTION

There is a gainsaying that is rampant to almost all the nations or (countries). What is the gain say? It goes that every nation or country is working towards ensuring national unity, cohesion and development. It is pertinent, that every nations deemed it useful to uniquely scath out of achieving this objective. Many structured programmes while others came up with other firms of organized groups, including corps groups, as a means or tool for getting national unity.

What is vital in this question that emanates, is to know what corps means? A corps is an entity or persons who mingles together, with the aim of indulging in teams activities or events. It is also an act under

members of a corps to carry out activities or Service that will enhance the nation, communities and among themselves.

Chile (2020) opined that a service is an organized involvement that enhances the benefit of a National State and Communities in which the corps member is rendering the services.

Pascal (2023) stated that the services of corps members is very crucial in the society and cannot be avoided, corps member get involved in certain activities that will enhance the nation unity and development.

Therefore, our country attach less importance to the services of corps in the society. These people are been paid token at the end of the month as an allowance to them. The meage salary given to corps members in our nation or society is barbaric and an insult to the services of the corps in our dear nation. Corpers as an individual stomached their difficulties because of their willingness and determination to serve their fatherland, but, they are not well-treated as important element in our country.

Oku (2021) opined that National Youth Service Corps Programme actualize our dreams by bringing us together, ensure showing of ideas and unity among our States. It is a youthful programme to a help us inculcate spirit of relationship and proper identification as an individual and nation. The National Youth Service Corps was introduced in the year 1973 by President, Gown with a genuine taught of bringing every state and individual therein together as one nation. The vision of President Gown has yielded a good result and has helped the nation to a achieve a lot in the areas of human services and ideas to enhance national unity and development.

Objectives of NYSC Programme

The main vision of NYSC is to rebuild and reconcile our differences, through bringing the youth together and ensure love and effective relationship. The establishment of NYSC has engender discipline and cohesion among youths in one country's by refusing in them a culture of work and loyal service to Nigeria in so many areas they may find themselves (NYSC, 2020) specially, the objectives of the programme are as follows:

- (i) To imbibe a culture of unity, love and cordial relationship.
- (ii) To encourage healths, relationship among Nigerian Universities and Polytechnic graduates between the required age for Youths Service.
- (iii) To motivate youths in Nigeria to render services to their fatherland.
- (iv) To encourage youths to have mind of self-acquired skills that will help them forget behind and withstand the task ahead of them.
- (v) To make youths cultivate right sense of belonging.
- (vi) To help youths remove or jettison discrimination among themselves.
- (vii) To make Nigerian Youths acquire a good living standard.
- (viii) To encourage love among one another.
- (ix) To encourage the Nigerian Youth Service Corps to embrace skills and ensure know time wasted.

In this developments, NYSC as a scheme or programme has made youths to imbibe spirit of interstate cultures and made of living in different ways. The programme have extensively bring out the talents of our youth in various ways as they embark on their fatherland services. The programme has exposed youths to be good managers and directors in life management as a youth.

The success of NYSC?

NYSC have achieve tremendously. It is a programme that has consulted youths of Nigeria in so many ways:

The ways are as follows:

- (i) Encourages spirit of integration and cultural understanding of other states and villages.
- (ii) The success of this noble programme. hinges in encouraging inter-tribal marriages and co-operation.
- (iii) The success of NYSC in Nigeria is in the areas of skills in which the youths acquire yearly.

- (iv) NYSC programmes has achieved a lot in the areas of man power development and craftsmanship.
- (v) The success of it also helps in bring youths, guidance and parents together.
- (vi) It also encourages sports and mentorship among Nigeria youths.

Need for Encouraging NYSC Programme

The reasons why NYSC should be encouraged among the youths in Nigeria is because it will encourage self-reliance, spirit of love and it will give Nigeria youth rightful sense of belonging. The programme will make youth to be self-employed and engage in inter-marriage. Too, majority of the Nigeria youth are unemployment, but the encouragements of the programme has made 47% of the youths to be employed and also to be creative. It is pertinent, the advise the government of Nigeria to make NYSC programme more proactive and lively.

The programme has made a lot of youth to be responsible and be proud of answering a Nigerian citizens. The Nigeria youths are more self-employed now than before because the constitution of NYSC programme.

Enriching the NYSC Programme with Entrepreneurship Education

One of the viable way of enriching NYSC programme to achieve its noble objectives of self-employment of corps members is by incorporating entrepreneurship education into the programme. In this development, serving corps members should be encourage or helped to become entrepreneurship experts after their service. For them to be entrepreneurship expert. It will jettison depressions and ensure there is food in their table (Chile, 2020).

What is Entrepreneurship Education?

Jackson (2025) opined that entrepreneur is a person who makes a finance through engaging in a running business that requires financial risk. Amadiola (2024) sees entrepreneurship education as an education embedded in identifying necessary needs.

Ude (2022) sees entrepreneur education as an arts of education based on vocational or career development which aimed at showcasing ones intellectual skills and development.

Baddey (2023) sees entrepreneurship education based on formal education. This is the type of education that brings about individual capacity in skills and individual well-being.

The Enrichment of NYSC Programme Anchored in Three Major Sensitive Areas

The areas are as follows:

1. **Primary Assignment Areas:** This is perceived after camp orientation as a serving corps members posted to various areas of values. Such as schools, Local Government and companies etc. The essence of this, is to make the corps member a temporary employees with a meager token called allowee. The money is paid every month till the end of the service year. The programme last for one year calendar month.
2. **Orientation State:** This is a situation that requires a duly corps member to be subjected to an orientation on how to follow up his/her service year. Orientation helps a corps member to know the do's and don'ts which must be communicated to them in orientation camp. Orientation camp helps in bringing corps members to informations that will guide them while performing their civic responsibility as corps member (Ala, 2021).
3. **Community Development Service CDS) Stage:** This is a stage that every corps member is expected to carry out their service delivery in hire with NYSC constitution. This stage demands them to carry out self-project were they are posted to serve, the CDS showcases true picture of the corps members as a citizen of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. CDS is observed every weak, some two times in a week and it is a compulsory service to render,

Implications for Reducing Youth Unemployment in Nigeria

Nigeria is a cosmopolitan country that depends majorly in oil which has been their source of economic survival. So, the introduction of NYSC programme today has metamorphosed the economy shape of Nigeria. The economic look in Nigeria is no longer what it is today. The rationale behind the development is the sky rocketing conditions of the oil in the major manacles internationally. The rise affected every areas, thereby causing youth unemployment in Nigeria. Every year many Nigeria youth complete. Their service year and face the labour minced for survival but, all their efforts proves futile. The role of unemployment among Nigerian youth is alarming and have call for attention.

Nda (2020) opined that youth should be properly equipped to withstand the occurring challenges through having spirit of developing themselves skillfully. Self-employment or trade will help to radiant youths vision and make them live meaningful life in the society. It is imperative, for corps members the adopts entrepreneurship (training) that will put food in their tables. Entrepreneurship ideas will assist Nigeria Youths to be independent and focus will corps members should learn how the save their token in order to start-up businesses that will make them rich in life and stop demand on government job.

CONCLUSION

It is pertinent and notable that entrepreneurship education is the have make of empowering youths financial. So, there is much to enrich the NYSC programme with entrepreneurship education.

In the develop, every corps members should embrace entrepreneurship ideas and skills during their service year because it is good to acquire skills.

Corps members should have entrepreneurship vision on target to live a meaningful life in the society and avoid depending in government job.

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